

The Effect Of EHSAN On The Conversion Or Decline Of Boundaries From The Perspective Of Islamic Jurists And Different Legislative Periods In Iran

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
January 01 , 2022

Accepted:
August 01 , 2022

Keywords :

Jurisprudence, Ehsan,
Hudud, Stoning, Volume

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.6949665

Abstract

The situation of perpetrators of some crimes has been and is one of the important factors in determining punishment by Islamic jurists and the legislators of our country. Ehsan, a man and a woman, is an effective factor in the conversion or decline of hadd. Divorce, disputes between couples cause the perpetrator to leave the marriage. In determining the punishment for crimes, the Iranian legislature has followed the opinion of the jurists to a greater extent and has predicted the heaviest punishments (stoning and murder) for the perpetrators of adultery and sodomy. Ehsan has no effect on the punishment of the perpetrators. However, the lack of Ehsan conditions in the person being qazf causes the hadd to fall.

Introduction

In Islamic law, the heaviest punishments for committing crimes have been imposed, but the evidence to prove them is limited and specific, and proving them is difficult and sometimes impossible, and on the other hand, the methods of punishment are easy and possible. Determining punishment for perpetrators of crimes to some extent, indecency depends on several factors, including the determinants of punishment, the situation of the perpetrator while committing a crime. The number of men and women committing adultery and the number of perpetrators of sodomy have a great impact on determining the punishment of the accused for committing the mentioned crimes. The general punishment of the perpetrator will disappear. Allegations that the defendant or his defense counsel lacked the necessary conditions during the trial can change the course of the case and dramatically change the punishment of the perpetrator.

Although the jurists and legislators have declared the punishment of a man and a woman to be murdered or stoned; However, they did not explicitly state the conditions for the realization of Ehsan and the cases of the perpetrator leaving, and in some cases they remained silent. On the other hand, the development of societies and the use of high-speed vehicles by human beings has raised questions about excuses such as travel as one of the cases of men and women leaving Ehsan, or the separation of couples after a divorce in the days of a couple and a woman living in a separate house. It raises questions in the minds of whether the new circumstances of the man and woman, the perpetrator of a certain crime out of favor or not?

The present article is in the position of expressing the conditions of realization and cases of leaving the court and its effect on some crimes, and we have tried to answer the questions raised from the perspective of great jurists and different legislative periods in our country.

1- Ehsan in words and terms

Ehsan in the word means to establish and strengthen, to keep the soul from doing bad deeds (Farhang-e Farsi Moin, p. 82) means to protect and preserve, and it also means to marry a man and to marry a woman.

In the term of Ehsan criminal jurisprudence, it is to protect oneself from immorality, and a person who protects himself from committing an act contrary to chastity through marriage is called a muhsin (I am not a jurist, vol. 5, p. 83) that committing adultery in this situation intensifies the punishment. It turns from enduring flogging to stoning, which is why it is also called stoning. The Holy Qur'an says, "And think that they will prevent them from rejoicing in God" (Al-Hashr, verse 14). The castles were called fortresses because the castles protected man from the evil of the enemy. What is meant here is that having a wife is a fortress that protects a man and a woman from committing sins, and if they commit indecency with a non-wife by having a wife and husband, their punishment will be doubled.

Some have said: The Qur'an does not mention stoning and adultery; But Ravandi quotes some commentators that in two places (Isra ' / 17, 32-33; An'am / 151, 6) after forbidding adultery and considering it an ugly and disgusting way, he says: Never the honorable soul who God forbid his killing, kill him, unless he deserves to be killed. And do not approach the adulterer ... and do not kill the soul that is forbidden to God

except with the truth; "... As a result, committing adultery is one of the cases of entitlement to murder (in the form of stoning), which is mentioned in these verses."

It is stated in a famous hadith that the Prophet (PBUH) said: It is not permissible for a Muslim to shed blood, except for one of three things: disbelief after faith (apostasy), adultery after Ehsan, killing someone unjustly (Al-Khalaf, Sheikh Tusi, vol. 5). P. 365 and Masalak Shahid Thani, Chapter Hudood).

2- Types of Ehsan: Islamic jurists have stated the reasons for the realization of Ehsan as follows:

1. EHSAN having a spouse
2. EHSAN due to chastity
3. EHSAN due to freedom
4. EHSAN because of Islam
5. EHSAN due to puberty

In this research, we will only deal with the first and second types of Ehsan and its effect on the limits from a jurisprudential and legal perspective.

3- Conditions for the fulfillment of a man's benevolence in adultery and sodomy

The jurists have stated conditions for the fulfillment of a man's benevolence, which are briefly as follows.

1. Hitting - entering (closeness) to the spouse so that it becomes junub and ghusl becomes obligatory.
2. Puberty - is approaching puberty.
3. Be wise - the condition of reason in the realization of a man's fortune is a point of contention.
4. Be free and not be a slave to anyone.
5. Introduction from the forehead - the vagina must be in the vulva and penetration from the forehead is not enough.
6. Have a permanent spouse and having a temporary spouse is not enough.
7. When a man proves to his permanent wife; By confessing the man or presenting evidence against him.
8. In the morning and in the afternoon (afternoon), he should be able to have sexual interest, that is, he should have his wife whenever he wants.
9. Previous intimacy should be with an adult woman. That is, his wife must also be an adult at the time, and therefore intimacy with an immature woman is not enough to achieve goodness.

4- Conditions for the realization of a woman's virtue

1. Puberty - It is a condition for a woman to be an adult during sexual intercourse, so if a minor has sexual intercourse with her husband and then commits adultery during puberty, it is not permissible.
2. Perfection of intellect - It is a condition that a woman be wise during intercourse with her husband, and the former intercourse in the absence of perfection of intellect removes her from adultery.
3. Freedom - The woman must be free and married. Do not be a slave or aunt.
4. Having a permanent spouse - Having a spouse in a temporary marriage does not make a woman happy.
5. Entry is done. That is, the previous closeness to the amount of hashfa and more so that ghusl is obligatory on him.
6. It is possible to have sexual intercourse with the husband through acceptance.

According to the jurists, the provision of intimacy in the morning and evening is valid only for men. And in Article 226 of the Islamic Penal Code of 1992, the legislator has mentioned the phrase "whenever he wants" only in paragraph A of the mentioned article in the case of a man, so the provision of a field of intimacy in the morning and evening is not valid for women.

It should be noted that there is disagreement among Islamic scholars about the condition of Islam (Muslim women and men adultery). Sunni, Hanifa and Maliki jurists believe that Islam is one of the conditions of Ehsan (Uthman ibn Ali al-Bar'i, p. 172; Abu al-Qasim ibn Jazi al-Kalbi al-Garnati, p. 233; Muhammad ibn Abd al-Rahman al-Maghribi, vol. 8, p. 395) Among the Hanafi jurists, Abu Yusuf believes that in Ehsan, Islam is not a condition (Shams al-Din al-Sarkhsi, p. 236). Ibn Qadama Hanbali also believes that Islam is not a condition for adultery in Ehsan, and if the people of Dhimma commit adultery while in Ehsan, their punishment is stoning. Among the Imami jurists, some jurists have considered the adultery of a woman as a condition and issued a fatwa on it (Sheikh Saduq Ibn Babawiyah, p. 439; Allama Hali, p. 137) and some have rejected the condition of the wife being a Muslim (Sheikh Mufid, p. 775; Sheikh Tusi). Finally, p. 693; Seyed Morteza, Al-Istifta ', p. 258).

One of the contemporary jurists, Ayatollah Sobhani, believes that there is no condition in Ehsan Islam, and if he has an adulterer, a Christian woman or a Jewish woman, and he commits adultery, it is permissible, because they have a lawful way. 89 - Available on the website of the School of Jurisprudence).

5- Cases of men and women leaving Ehsan

5-1- Absence of each couple from each other

5-2- Lack of access to each other. The man's access to the woman and the woman's obedience to him is the right of the man, but the jurists have not given the woman the right to have intercourse with her whenever she wants.

5-3- The disease prevents sexual intercourse, such as menstruation and infertility in a man, menstruation, puerperium, and a century in women.

5-4- Diseases (diseases) that cause danger to the other party, such as: AIDS, syphilis, gonorrhoea and hepatitis

5-5- Travel - Absence and distance of each couple from each other in a way that they cannot have sexual intercourse with each other. From the well-known point of view of the jurists, the criterion for the fulfillment of Ehsan is the customary ability and incapacity of the spouse, whether it is a religious journey or not. Also, religious and non-religious travel has no effect on the obstacle of travel as one of the obstacles to the realization of Ehsan and the criterion is to have customary ability. The Second Branch of the Supreme Court, in its decision No. 9/2/58, has considered the distance of four farsakhs, citing a fatwa from the Imam (ra) in the book *Judicial Criteria*, as the issue of 49 distances from leaving Ehsan.

5-6- Each couple is in prison

5-7- Occurrence of divorce between couples. The great jurists consider only the occurrence of Bain divorce to be effective in removing the couple from Ehsan and do not consider reciprocal divorce as an obstacle to Ehsan. However, considering that the couple is separated from each other due to the occurrence of a dispute and the woman is no longer living in the man's house and they do not have access to each other, it can be said that with the divorce and separation of the couple, they are out of wedlock. have become. In the Penal Code of 1991, this matter was provided for in Article 85, but the new law approved in 1992 is silent in this regard.

5-8- Existence of intense differences and hatred between couples. This condition is not mentioned in jurisprudential books and has not been discussed; However, in recent inquiries from contemporary jurists, some of them, including Makarem Shirazi, Seyyed Abdul Karim Mousavi Ardabili, Lotfollah Safi Golpayegani, Hossein Nouri Hamedani, Bashiri Zanjani, and Mohammad Taghi Behjat, consider this issue an obstacle. Of course, it can be said that when there is a suspicion about the limits, it is possible to get rid of the couple by resorting to the rule. The Second Branch of the Supreme Court, in its decision No. 285- 25/5/71, has commented that the difference between couples and the lack of sexual intercourse between them can get them out of trouble.

5-9- Lack of special obedience of the wife to the husband, in which case the said man is not a prostitute, but the said wife is a prostitute in case of committing adultery.

5-10- Pregnancy of a woman - The Fourth Branch of the Supreme Court in its decision No. 472- 14/7/70 has considered the pregnancy of a woman and the absence of permission for intimacy for six months as Muscat's Ehsan.

6- The effect of EHSAN in Hudud from the perspective of Islamic jurists

6-1- The effect of EHSAN on adultery

There is no difference between the jurists of Islam regarding the punishment of adultery and adultery, and they unanimously agree that their punishment is stoning. Except for the Kharijites who do not accept the punishment of stoning and say that stoning does not exist in the Shari'a and does not appear in the Qur'an and in the successive tradition (Al-Khalaf, vol. 5, p. 365). The document of Sunni jurists about the punishment of stoning, the consensus of the ummah and the Sunnah is consistent (Ibn Hazm al-Andalusi, *ibid.*). Imami jurists have unanimously considered the punishment of adultery to be stoning, but they disagree on whether in addition to the punishment of stoning, the punishment of leprosy is also imposed on adultery and adultery, which is stated below:

Well-known jurists: Most of the jurists, including Sheikh Tusi, Qazi Ibn al-Baraj, Fadhil Meqdad, Ibn Hamza, Mohaqeq Hali, Imam Khomeini (ra) and Ayatollahs ... Khomeini and Sahib Jawahir (ra) say: If adultery and adultery are both Muhassin and both of them are young and we only stone them (Sheikh Tusi, 5/366, 1409; Al-Tripoli, Ibn al-Baraj, 2/519, 1406; Fadhil Miqdad, 4/337, 1343; Ibn Hamza Tusi, 411, 1408; Imam Khomeini - Rohwa ..., 4/333, 1369; Mohaghegh Hali, 4/936, 1374; Ayatollah ... Khomeini, 1/191, 1976; Najafi - Mohammad Hassan, 41/318, 1363).

The arguments of those who believe in the popular opinion: Consensus of movable and productive - The owner of the jewel says: I have not seen any violation in this issue and there are both types of consensus of movable and productive.

Narrations _ The authentic narration of Sama'a from Abi 'Abda ... (AS) who said: ... But the adulterous man and the adulterous woman, then stoning is obligatory on them (Ameli - Horr, 34/187, 1403).

Unfamiliar opinion: Some jurists, including the first martyr, the second martyr, the owner of Riyadh, Samiri and Ibn Fahd Hali, believe that Mohsen and Mohsen I was flogged and then stoned (Shahid Thani, Zin al-Din bin Ali Al-Ameli, 9 / 86-85, 1414; Tabatabai-Seyyed Ali, 10/46, 1412; Samiri-Fallah Ibn Hassan, 3/220, 14085; Ibn Fahd Hali, 5/27, 1413).

Evidences of those who believe in the unpopular: Narrations: Zararah has quoted Imam Mohammad Baqir (AS) that the Imam (AS) has said about the punishment of Muhsin and Muhsin: first hit him with a hundred lashes and then stone them (Har Ameli, 18 / 343-1403).

The reason of the martyrs (the first martyr - the second martyr) about the infamous opinion (volume and stoning): The first martyr says: the sum is between Surah Noor verse 2 and the narration and the second martyr says that the stronger promise is the one that the first martyr took and the reason for this theory Sahih indicates this ruling, and when the Commander of the Faithful (pbuh) whipped and stoned an adulterous woman, he said:

I flogged her according to the Book of God and stoned her according to the tradition of the Messenger of God (pbuh). They elaborated between the young person and the old person, it is a narration that they are not authorized to cite both in terms of the text and the document (Shahid Thani, Zayn al-Din ibn Ali al-Ameli, 9/86, 1414).

Regarding the punishment of unmarried men and women, mainly Sunni and Imami jurists agree that the punishment for such a person is a cover, and their document is verse 2 of Surah Noor, which states: However, they do not agree on the sentence of exile in addition to the cover. Hanifa do not believe in this gathering and do not accept the punishment of exile (Muhammad ibn Hassan Tusi, Al-Mabsut, 1387, vol. 9, p. 44). Contrary to this view, the Shafi'is, Hanbalis, and Malikis, in addition to the punishment of a certain extent, consider the punishment of exile (one year) (Mansour ibn Yunus al-Bahouti, *ibid.*, P. 117). Shiite jurists also believe that if a woman who is in a state of adultery commits adultery with a (immature) boy, her punishment will be the same (Najafi, Jawaher, p. 321).

6-2- The effect of EHSAN on sodomy

There is disagreement among jurists as to whether or not a sodomite is killed. Well-known jurists believe that he will be killed; However, the late Khoei, the owner of the foundations of completing the curriculum, in the opinion of the famous jurists, creates problems and believes that the non-Mohsen will not be killed and will only be flogged. Their problem is as follows:

The reason for our problems is that apparently the Shiite jurists agree that there is no difference between sodomy and non-sodomy in sodomy. It has been attributed and consensus has been claimed in the writings of some jurists, and if there is a consensus on this issue [otherwise between sodomy and non-adultery in sodomy], otherwise there is room for a wide-ranging debate on this issue. There are several categories of narrations in this regard.

The first category - the narrations which indicate that killing a sodomite [the perpetrator in the act of sodomy is not the object] [it is absolutely obligatory whether he is a prostitute or not] and murder is not bound to be a prostitute], including the correct narrations of the owner Ibn Atiyah is one of Imam Sadiq (as) who said: The Commander of the Faithful (AS) was among a group of his companions when suddenly a man came to him and said: O Commander of the Faithful, I have had sodomy with a boy. So, cleanse me [by performing the hadd of this sin] to the extent that he says that when he confessed in the fourth time, the Prophet (pbuh) said to him: The act should be ugly. The Imam said:

The second category - there are narrations that indicate that a sodomite will be killed if he is a mahsin, but if he is not a mahsin, he will be flogged, like Mu'tabarah Hammad Ibn Uthman who says: I said to Imam Sadiq (as): A man had sodomized another man] [They said: "If he is a mahsan, he will be killed, and if he is not a mahsan, he will be flogged." I said: What will happen to a person who has become an object? They said: "He will be killed in any case, whether he is a Muhsin or a non-Muhsin" (*Ibid.*, Chapter 1, Hadith 4).

The third category is the narrations which indicate that if [a sodomite] is a prostitute, he will be stoned [not killed with a sword], and if he is not a prostitute, he will be flogged. Among them is the authoritative Hussein ibn Alwan from Imam Ja'far Sadegh from his father from Imam Ali (as) who said, "If he was a sodomite, if he is a mahsin, the limit of stoning and if he is not a sodomite, the limit of flogging will be imposed on him" (*ibid.* - Hadith 6) and the authoritative Yazid. Ibn Abd al-Malik, who said that he heard Imam al-Baqir (as) say: Hadd stoning And if he has committed adultery [and it also applies to the man if] he is in sodomy Whether he is a Muhsin or a non-Muhsin (*ibid.* - Hadith 8) and the Sahih of Ibn Abi Umayr from some of our companions from Imam Sadiq (as) who said about a person who had sodomy: He is a whip if he is not a prostitute "(*Ibid.* - Chapter 3 of the chapters on sodomy - Hadith 1) It should not be [with the narrations of the second category] that it says that if Muhassin is a murderer, we should whip him [in such a way that in the case of Muhassin we sentence him to death and in the case of a non-Muhassin, we order him to be flogged. The stoning of a sodomite is obligatory According to its application, it is necessary that stoning is obligatory [not optional, that is, the same stoning must be carried out, and the person does not have the right to choose the other two types of punishment: throwing from a mountain and setting fire [as required by Malik ibn Atiyah]. The first category [is that murder is committed in one of the three ways mentioned in that narration, so we must refrain from applying any of these narrations according to the text of the other narration, and as a result [between killing a sodomite] between stoning and We are free to mention the three cases mentioned in that narration [murder with a sword - throwing from a mountain - burning in a fire], and in this case, if there is a consensus that there is none, otherwise we must distinguish between the virtuous and the non-virtuous.] In such a way that the stoning is carried out on Mohsen and the other three cases on non-Mohsen [; But according to the theory that we have expressed, that the statement is that if the sodomizer is not a prostitute, he will not be killed. "

As for the person who is in passive sodomy; According to the consensus of Imami jurists, he is killed and it does not matter whether he is a muhsin or not. The reason for this is the narrations included in this regard, among which are Sahih Yazid ibn Abdul Malik and Sahih Hamad ibn Uthman, which were mentioned above, and Sahih Ja'far ibn Muhammad from Abdullah ibn Maimun from Imam Sadiq (as) who says: Khalid ibn Abu Bakr wrote a letter that said: You and then, a man was brought to me who was given evidence that he gives himself to

others for sodomy as a woman commits adultery, and in this case Abu Bakr (the first caliph) consulted with others and they said that he then consulted with the Commanders of the Faithful, Ali (as), who said: "Burn him in the fire ..." (Mustadrak al-Wasail, chapter 5 of the chapters of Hadd sodomy, hadith 9).

Sunni jurists agree on the sanctity of sodomy, but there is a serious disagreement between them on the type of mixed punishment and whether sodomy is subject to a limited punishment or ta'zir. According to Malik and according to a narration according to Ahmad Hanbal, the punishment of laity and mixed (active and passive) is murder (Malik ibn Anas, *Al-Muta*, vol. 2, p. 825; Abu al-Qasim Ibn Jazi al-Kalbi Garnati, p. 233). However, it has been narrated from Malik that the punishment for laity and mixed is stoning (Malik Ibn Anas, *Al-Madunah Al-Kubra*, vol. 6, p. 213). Also, the companions of the Prophet (PBUH) have a consensus in issuing the sentence of murder. It has also been narrated from the Prophet (PBUH): "I rejoiced in the deeds of the people of Lot, but killed the active and the passive." Of course, in the type of murder, there are various narrations, including being killed with a sword, being thrown from a mountain, and being burned (Abu Muhammad Abdullah Ibn Qadameh, *Al-Mughni*, vol. 10, p. 161).

In the meantime, some Hanbali jurists consider the punishment of laity as adultery, which if sentenced to stoning and otherwise, to one hundred lashes (volume) and one year in exile (Mansour bin Younis Al-Bahouti, *Kashaf al-Qana'*, p. 120). Shafi'i jurists also believe in this detailed view, with the difference that if Lait was a prisoner, he would be sentenced to death, otherwise he would be entitled to imprisonment and exile for one year. The object in sodomy (mixed) is not punished if it is minor or insane or cunning

But if a person is obliged, he is entitled to imprisonment and exile, and in this case, it does not matter whether he is a muhsin or a non-muhsin (Sheikh Muhammad al-Sharhini al-Khatib, *Mughni al-Muhtaj*, p. 144; Abu Ishaq Ibrahim ibn Yusuf al-Shirazi, *al-Madhhab ...*, p. 339). The document of this group of jurists is the narrations in which it is stated, "If the man's man understands the ignorant" (Sheikh Muhammad al-Sherhini al-Khatib, the same). They believe that in the crime of sodomy, *Ilaj Faraj* is located in Faraj and has the ruling of adultery. In fact, a person who does not have the right to occupy the vulva commits a forbidden act and commits adultery according to the generality of verses and news (Shah Malekpour, 2015, p. 54).

Abu Hanifa, unlike other Sunni religions, believes that sodomy is not a local crime for Wati. Consequently, in the act of committing sodomy, only the perpetrator deserves ta'zir because it is a sin (Shokani, *ibid.*, p. 288). In fact, Abu Hanifa does not consider wati in *debar*, whether in men or women, to be subject to hadd, although he believes in the sanctity of this practice (Ibn Najim al-Masri, *Bahr al-Ra'iq*, p. 27).

Kasani writes in this regard that from Abu Hanifa's point of view, sodomy is fundamentally different from adultery - adultery is the same as before women - and therefore the punishment for adultery is not applied to the sodomite. The fact that once it is customary to say that someone sodomized but did not commit adultery or it is said that he committed adultery but did not commit sodomy is the reason why these two titles, in addition to being different in name, also differ in meanings. For this reason, there is disagreement among the companions regarding the punishment of sodomy, while there is no such difference in the punishment of adultery. In adultery, lineage is wasted, whereas in sodomy this is not the case. Adultery is a common thing that requires rejection and suffering by the legislator, but sodomy is not a common and common thing that does not necessarily require severe punishment for suffering and rejection. Therefore, ta'zir has been determined for the punishment of sodomy, the amount and characteristics of which are in the hands of the judge and are determined in proportion to the act committed (Aladdin Al-Kasani, *Bada'i al-Sana'i*, p. 34).

In fact, Hanafi jurists believe that what has been said in the narrations about killing the subject and the object can be attributed to the fact that either expediency has prevailed or the mixture of this act has been considered lawful. Therefore, what is obligatory to kill is subject to sodomy. If a person becomes addicted to sodomy, the Imam can kill the laity in terms of the policy of discipline and ta'zir (Ibn Najim al-Masri, *Al-Bahr al-Ra'iq*, p. 28).

In the meantime, Ibn Hazm, in an analysis of the issue of sodomy, denies the extent of the crime and writes that those who believe in stoning or murder argue that this act was the act of the people of Lot and is not considered correct in the Qur'an because stoning is punishable, because The people of Lot were not only punished for committing sodomy, but, according to the text of the Qur'an, because they had become infidels (a lie of the people of Lot), stoning was carried out on them (Shah Malekpour, 1394, p. 55). In the meantime, several narrations have been narrated from the Prophet (PBUH) in which the murders of criminals have been limited and confined. As narrated from the Prophet (PBUH): "Muslim blood is permissible except for three things: disbelief after faith, committing adultery and committing murder." And sodomy has no place in this. As in the narrations indicating some punishments, there is no mention of sodomy. Finally, it can be said that since the subject and the object have committed sins in committing sodomy and have committed denial - and the prohibition of denial is also obligatory - they deserve to be punished (Ibn Hazm al-Andalsi, *Al-Mahali*, pp. 384-385).

Of course, in the crime of sodomy, the majority of Sunni jurists agree with the punishment to some extent. As Ibn Qadameh, while agreeing to the murder of Lait and Mulut, writes that the promise to fall is contrary to the text and consensus, and it is basically incorrect to compare the vulva (*Dabr*) with anything else, because *Dabr* is

not a place to be close and close to what may happen in There is a difference between couples 'sexual relations (such as intimacy), because in couples' relations, there is the right of possession anyway (Abu Muhammad Abdullah Ibn Qadameh, Al-Mughni, vol. 10, p. 186).

6-3- The effect of Ehsan on the extent of tafkhiz

Famous opinion of jurists: If sodomy without penetration was in the form of sexual intercourse or sexual operations between two male thighs, it would be a hundred lashes on the subject and object. He has said and all the later ones are of this opinion., 1376) and Fakhr al-Muhaqiqin also believes in this opinion (Explanation of Benefits, vol. 4, 492, 1378).

Reasons: 1- Consensus

2- Narrations: A narration narrated by Sulayman ibn Hilal from Imam Sadegh (AS) that a man commits sodomy with a man. (hor ameli 1403 416 ◌).

The owner of the jewel says: Although this narration is weak, but its weakness has been compensated by obvious action and consensus, and apparently the meaning of hadd in this narration is flogging (Jawahar al-Kalam, Najafi-Mohammad Hassan, vol. 41, 382, 1363).

The principle of not having to kill is to be careful in shedding blood.

Unfamiliar opinion: Sheikh Tusi has said in the end, contrary to and extended: in sodomy without entering, if a person is a mahsan, he will be stoned and if he is not a mahsan, he will be flogged and Shahid Thani has quoted this promise from a judge who says: By doing so, he wanted to combine the narrations that say that sodomy is like adultery and the narrations that say that a sodomite is killed by interpreting the first category as sodomy without penetration and the second category as sodomy with penetration. Allameh Hilli has said in quoting this promise in various Shiites (Jawahar al-Kalam, Najafi-Mohammad Hassan, vol. 41, 382, 1363) (Allameh Hilli, vol. 9, 189, 1376; Shahid Thani, vol. 9, 150, 1414).

Reasons: Narration (plural between narrations): Between the narration of Ala 'Ibn Fadhil from Imam Sadegh (AS) who said: The hadd of sodomy is like the hadd of an adulterer and then they said that if the sodomite is a prostitute, he will be stoned and otherwise he will be flogged. And the narration of Hammad ibn Uthman is close to the same theme, and a combination should be made between the narration that condemns the sodomite as absolute (whether he is a Muhsin or a non-Muhsin) (Shahid Thani, Al-Rawdah al-Bahiyyah, vol. 9, 151, 1414).

Argument of the owner of the jewel in rejecting the reason of the mentioned theory (sum of narrations): The owner of the jewel says: The sum of the narrations is if those narrations are equal in every respect, but here the second category narrations which in any case have determined the punishment of sodomy is preferable and it is in accordance with the principles and rules of religion, so the plural has no meaning (Jawahar al-Kalam, Najafi-Mohammad Hassan, vol. 41, 383, 1363).

Sheikh Saduq and his father and Scafi say: In absolute sodomy, whether it is accompanied by penetration or not (tafkhiz), their punishment is murder (whether it is fornication or non-fornication) (Allameh Hali, vol. 9, 189, 1997; Najafi, vol. 9, 189, 1997).

Reasons: The narration of Hudhayfah Ibn Mansour is that there is no sodomy but the infidelity is to God (Waseel, Sheikh Har Ameli, vol. 18, Hadith 2 and 3, 257, 1403).

The owner of the jewel's argument in rejecting the above-mentioned narrations: The owner of the jewel says: First, these two narrations are weak compared to other narrations and cannot be opposed to them. Najafi, vols. 41, 383, 1363).

Shahid Thani's point of view in rejecting the narrations: Shahid Thani says: The narration to which the two parties (the first theory and the second theory are not famous) are not reliable in terms of document, and the certainty of the famous saying (which is a hundred lashes) and the principle That is, there is no fixed punishment other than flogging (Shahid Thani, vol. 9, 150, 1414).

6-4- The effect of EHSAN on the HADD of QAZF

One of the conditions for proving the hadd of qazf is the amount of qazf. Ehsan includes intellect, maturity, Islam and chastity. All of the above cases make the Qazf to be fulfilled (Ibn Rushd, ibid.; Mansour bin Yunus al-Bahouti, ibid., P. 134).

1) Wisdom and maturity: Crazy and immature Qazf is not conceivable at all, because they are not obligated and their adultery is not considered a crime. Therefore, their qazf is a kind of lie and causes ta'zir of the qazf (Aladdin Al-Kasani, ibid.). Shafi'i and Hanafi jurists also believe that forced qazf and promotion (those who are unable to have intimacy and sexual intercourse) are not subject to the hadd punishment of qazf, because it is not possible for them to commit adultery and attributing adultery to them is a lie and does not cause shame and blame. (Ibn Najim al-Masri, the same; Uthman ibn Ali al-Bar'i and ..., Explanation of the facts ..., p. 200) While Ibn Qadameh believes that there is no difference between forced qazf and other than him, because in every qazf, humiliation is inflicted on the accused person. And the ability of the abrogated to be close to something is hidden and hidden that most people are not aware of and is subject to the general products mentioned in the Qur'an and the rightful owner is abused, like a sick person who is abused (Abu Muhammad Abdullah Ibn Qadameh, ibid.,

P. 203). Other Hanbali jurists also believe that qazf is valid if it is obligatory (one who does not have a penis) or promoted (Mansour ibn Yunus al-Bahouti, *ibid.*, P. 133).

In this regard, Ibn Hazm believes that even a childish and insane qazf is subject to the hadd qazf and is included in a verse of the Qur'an, which states: It is forbidden to commit adultery, and certainly children and lunatics are also forbidden from adultery, and it is certainly acceptable for them to lie. For this reason, their denial is definitely a lie and the denier deserves to be punished.

Either it is qazf or it is correct (the attributor has actually done the attributed work); Or it is probable that truth and falsehood have a limit; Or it is certainly a lie that still has a limit (Ibn Hazm al-Andalus, *ibid.*, Pp. 273-274).

2) Chastity: It is one of the constituent elements of Ehsan, meaning free from committing adultery that causes severe punishment (Ibn Najim Masri, *ibid.*, P. 35; Aladdin al-Kasani, *ibid.*, P. 41; Abu al-Barakat, *ibid.*, 326; Zakaria al-Ansari, Asni al-Mutalib, P. 275). Therefore, if the abrogator is a drunkard but is not known for committing adultery, the abuser will be entitled to the hadd (Mansour ibn Yunus al-Bahouti, *ibid.*, P. 135). Just as a person does not lose his chastity with a forbidden marriage (as if a man had intercourse with his wife during menstruation). This forbidden proximity, which is an incidental matter, does not make him chaste (Mohammad al-Sherbini al-Khatib, *ibid.*). The question is whether the attribute of chastity and not committing adultery should be continuous and continuous until the punishment of the perpetrator? In other words, if someone is called an adulterer and he commit adultery later, then is his perpetrator entitled to punishment or not?

Abu Hanifa, Malik, and Shafi'i do not believe in the punishment of the deceiver, because they consider the continuation of the description of chastity in the victim as a condition until the time of punishment (Al-Qarfani, Al-Zakhira, p. 102; P. 127).

In addition, committing adultery after qazf strengthens the qazf's promise and reveals the truth of his words, and can be an indication that he may have committed adultery before, such as the testimony of witnesses who committed adultery after martyrdom and before the execution of the sentence. This will lead to the annulment of the punishment.

Ibn Qadameh, while expressing the view of the jurists of the religions, does not believe in this matter and considers the Qadhif worthy of hadd. In other words, Masharalieh does not consider the continuation of the forbidden chastity as a condition until the execution of the punishment. In his opinion, it is certain that the abducted must have been chaste at the time of Qazf, that is, he must not have committed adultery. This will give rise to the right of qazf for the maqzuf, even if he commits it later, just as if the mazzufi goes insane after the qazf, his (qadf) right of qazf will not be revoked. Of course, it is said in jurisprudence that if the rightful owner becomes an apostate, his right will be lost, because apostasy causes the deterioration of rights and property, just as in order to testify, the justice of witnesses must be continuous until the execution of the punishment. The assumption is different (Abu Muhammad Abdullah Ibn Qadameh, *ibid.*, P. 220).

3) Being a Muslim: Islam is also one of the founding elements of Ehsan Muqzuf (Ibn Rushd, the same; Abu Muhammad Abdullah Ibn Qadameh, the same). According to the citation of "I am a polytheist with God, I am not a polytheist", the qazf of an infidel does not cause the hadd of qazf (Uthman bin Ali al-Bar'i et al., *Ibid.* ;

The point is that if the perpetrator does not meet the conditions of Ehsan, the perpetrator will be sentenced to a ta'zir punishment, because he has caused harassment to the addressee, which is not permissible (Abu Zakaria Muhiyat al-Din al-Nawawi, *ibid.*, P. 59).

Shia view

In the view of Shiite jurists, the concept of Ehsan has been proposed with the same four elements, maturity, intellect, Islam and chastity, and immature, crazy, non-Muslim and non-chaste Qazf is subject to the ruling of Ta'zir Seyed Ali Tabatabai, the same).

Chastity is the same as being free from adultery and sodomy and not pretending to them (Zayn al-Din Jabal Ameli (Shahid Thani), Masalak, vol. 14, p. 438). Therefore, if a person who has been subjected to hadd due to committing adultery, but has not yet repented, is given adultery, he is not subject to the hadd punishment of qazf (Sheikh Saduq Ibn Babawiyah, *ibid.*, P. 442). The religious document is the conditions mentioned for the narrators who have been quoted from the Imams (as)

In the Islamic Penal Code approved in 1392, the conditions of Ehsan to the extent of Qazf are the same as stated in jurisprudential books (Article 251). These conditions were also mentioned in Articles 146, 147 and 148 of the Islamic Penal Code approved in 1370.

Article 251 of the Islamic Penal Code adopted in 1392 states that "qazf causes hadd if the victim is adult, wise, Muslim, certain and does not pretend to commit adultery or sodomy."

Note 1- If the person who is qazf is immature, insane, insane, non-Muslim or indefinite, the person who is qazf shall be sentenced to thirty-one to seventy-four lashes of the sixth degree, but qazf for pretending to be adulterer or sodomite shall not be punished.

In the law of 1370, it was stated in Article 148 that if the qazf pretender to what has been attributed to him, the qazf has no hadd or ta'zir. Therefore, the lack of conditions for Ehsan in the abrogation causes the hadd to fall in the crime of Qazf.

7- The effect of EHSAN on HODUD from the perspective of different legislative periods in Iran

The issue of Ehsan was first raised in Article 207 of the General Penal Code of 1304. This article provided for the death penalty for perpetrators of sodomy and adultery. Of course, this article of the law was amended on 7/2/1310, and the crime of sodomy was removed from the phrase article and the words illegitimate relationship were used instead of adultery. . The article was amended again on September 20, 1941. This time, for the crime of sodomy, Article 207 of the amendment provided for imprisonment from three to 10 years. In the case of adultery, the legislator used the term insult to honor and only for the perpetrators of insulting the honor of women by force and reluctance provided for the punishment and regarding the condition of Ehsan in paragraph 6 of the article considered male marriage an aggravating factor He predicted, without stating the reasons for leaving Ehsan. Apparently, just having a wife for a man who committed a crime was enough to intensify his punishment.

It is added that in the mentioned law, there is no reference to the extent of tafkhiz and fornication, and it seems that sodomy also refers to sodomy of its conjugal type and does not include tafkhiz.

After the General Penal Code, the Law on Hudud, Diyat and Qisas was passed in 1361, in which the limit of sodomy was stated for the perpetrators of murder (Article 141) and there was no discussion of the number of the subject and the object; The limit of tafkhiz and the like was also stated as one hundred lashes for each subject and object (Article 52). In the case of fornication, the limit of one hundred lashes was mentioned and there was no discussion about the fate of the parties; Therefore, the non-adherence of the subject and the object did not have the effect of sodomy, and the adultery of the perpetrator had no effect on the aggravation of punishment.

In the Islamic Penal Code adopted in 1991, in Article 83 of the Legislation, after defining the adultery of an adulterous man and an adulterous woman, he stipulated the punishment of stoning for an adulterous man and woman who commit adultery. Had prescribed.

Regarding the limit of sodomy, in Article 108, by defining sodomy, he had divided it into agile sodomy and sodomy in a tafkhiz manner, and in the following articles, he had defined the aghad sodomy limit (in case of penetration) as murder and the tafkhiz limit as one hundred lashes. In this law, the legislator did not differentiate between a married man and a non-married man.

In addition, in this law, in the case of fornication, the limit of each of the parties was stated as one hundred lashes (AD-129) and no distinction was made between fornication and non-adultery, and in any case, the punishment for both parties were one hundred lashes.

In the Islamic Penal Code adopted in 1392, the punishment for adultery and adultery is stoning, and the first difference between this law and previous laws is the provision of alternative punishment for stoning, which is stated in Article 225. This article states: "The hadd punishment for adultery is stoning for adultery and adultery for stoning. "If it is not possible to carry out the stoning with the proposal of the court issuing the final verdict and the consent of the head of the judiciary, if the crime is proven, it will result in the execution of the adulterer and the adulterer, otherwise it will result in one hundred lashes for each." Due to the fact that proving adultery with evidence is difficult and impossible, so with the approval of this article, the punishment of stoning can be ruled out. In addition, in this law, the conditions for the realization of male and female sexual intercourse are more clearly defined and defined in Article 226, and the cases that exclude the perpetrator from sexual intercourse are stated in Article 227. Has been.

The second difference between this law and the previous laws is the level of sodomy. In this law, the punishment of sodomy (object) is stated in any circumstance (intentional and non-adulterous) of murder, because benevolence has no meaning for the object.

Another effect of Ehsan in the limits goes back to the evidence of these crimes, so that if adultery and sodomy are subject to stoning and murder, the quorum of witness testimony is only the testimony of four just men, and if it is other than stoning and murder, with the testimony of less than four men It can also be proved in addition to women. Crimes are two male witnesses, except in adultery, sodomy, fornication, and adultery, which are proved by four male witnesses. "In the law of 1991, adultery subject to stoning was also proven by the testimony of three men and two just women. The legislator returned from this sentence in 1392 and considered adultery subject to stoning and murder only with the testimony of four just men.

It should be noted that according to the new laws (Articles 241 of the Islamic Penal Code adopted in 1392 and 102 of the Code of Criminal Procedure adopted in 1392) And the possibility of committing a crime by force, reluctance, harassment or deception; Or the crime takes place in the public eye, in which case the prosecution and investigation is carried out only within the scope of the complaint or the obvious circumstances by the judge of the court.

This method of trial is based on the jurisprudential point of view, which prohibits the investigation of crimes against chastity and sexual behavior of individuals and tries to hide it. The jurists consider the sanctity of absenteeism and the spread of prostitution and the necessity of greater private parts as well as the sanctity of espionage, which can be found in verses 12 of the chapters "No spying and no greed in some of them" and 18 light of "those who love prostitution" as reasons. The narrations that indicate the boycott as well as the alleged consensus on this issue confirm this.

Considering the above, it seems that when the legislator has forbidden the investigation of these crimes, then the investigation is not justified to obtain a crime and obtain knowledge, and we can say that the judge's knowledge is not an argument in these crimes and the holy shari'a Proving it means not covering these crimes and covering them up.

Result

Islamic law and relevant laws in our country aggravate the punishment of the perpetrator of a certain crime, and the lack of this condition causes the punishment of stoning and murder to become a punishment of flogging. The perpetrator may be sentenced to ta'zir. The Iranian legislator has followed the hadd punishment of adultery and other limits for the perpetrator by having the conditions of Ehsan in the opinion of the famous jurists, but in the punishment for the perpetrator of sodomy, he has followed the type of punishment from the famous jurists. Which is an innovation and with the approval of Article 225 of the Islamic Penal Code in 1392, with the introduction of Article 225 of the Islamic Penal Code with a new innovation in relation to non-execution of stoning sentence and turning it into a punishment in cases of impossibility of execution of the sentence, a new chapter Has opened in this chapter, which can be said to be the result of dynamic jurisprudence studies at the present time.

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